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An Overview of the Effects of Climate Change and Eco-Degradation Through the Lens of Solastalgia in Select Novels

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Abstract:

Climate change due to the earth's warming, carbon emissions, overfishing, pollution, and flowing populations has worsened the livelihood of lifeforms in recent times. Anthropocene's over-exploitation is the major cause of environmental collapse. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and several climate mitigation and environmental policies urge humans to control and combat with climate crisis and to wisely act upon the conservation of nature. The selected works for the study include; *The Overstory* by Richard Powers, *Gold Fame Citrus* by Claire Vaye Watkins, and *The End of the Ocean* by Maja Lunde in the form of deforestation, extreme drought, and marine ecosystem depletion respectively, these works poignantly express the species extinction, ecological distress, survival angst. Solastalgia is one among the eco-psychological affect theories, which is based on the expression of the grief felt while remaining in a changing environment, especially one impacted by environmental degradation or climate change. Climate change intensifies solastalgia as more people witness extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, rising sea levels, and other

transformations to landscapes that were once stable and comforting. This proposed research paper overviews ecological degradation due to the effects of climate change in select novels from the perspective of solastalgia.

Keywords: Climate change, SDG Goals, Solastalgia, Eco-psychology, Climate mitigation.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is the world's greatest existential threat. If greenhouse gas emissions from burning fossil fuels are not reduced, hundreds and thousands of species would die extinct, entire towns would become uninhabitable, and massive crop and fishery catastrophes would occur due to rising global temperatures. Climate change is already causing suffering and mortality, even if these effects may still be avoidable. Today, its escalating effects are felt directly outside our windows as fierce storms and blazing wildfires. Understanding these impacts will help us better prepare and protect all communities for what is now happening, what can be avoided, and what is yet to happen.

People are eventually impacted by how climate change affects the environment, weather, wildlife, and agriculture. Throughout the world, our lifestyles from the businesses that sustain our economy to how we get our food, have developed in rather stable settings. Global warming threatens this foundation and has the power to alter society as a whole. In the worst situation, this could lead to mass malnutrition, disease, war, eviction, injury, and death. Many people around the world are already experiencing this terrible warning. Therefore, because of climate change, all human life is in danger of going extinct.

Air quality deteriorates due to climate change, increasing exposure to dangerous fumes from wildfires and ozone smog, which can lead to health problems, particularly for people with medical conditions. Approximately one billion individuals will be at risk of heat stress if the

average world temperature rises by two degree Celsius. Record-breaking heat waves claimed thousands of lives in 2022.

The primary international authority on climate science is the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), which was founded in 1988 by UNEP and WMO. It compiles and evaluates studies on the impact of climate change, its effects, and possible remedies. The IPCC publishes in-depth assessments, analyses a thorough comprehension of the causes and effects of global warming in addition to mitigation and adaptation tactics. According to its findings, humans are mostly responsible for climate change. The work of the IPCC directs International climate policies, such as the Paris Agreement.

To address the issues of global warming, climate mitigation involves taking steps to improve natural carbon sinks and lower greenhouse gas emissions. This entails supporting sustainable farming methods, increasing energy efficiency, switching to renewable energy, and developing technology like carbon capture. To slow down climate change and promote a more sustainable future, these initiatives are crucial. Promoting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is directly related to reducing climate change, especially regarding goals like living on land SDG 15, affordable and clean energy SDG 7, and climate action SDG 13.

In order to promote meaningful action, this advocacy focuses on increasing awareness, coordinating resources, and encouraging cooperation between governments, communities and corporations. A comprehensive strategy for creating a resilient and low-carbon future is ensured by incorporating climate mitigation into the SDG framework.

Solastalgia a portmanteau word, is derived from the combination of the Latin word ‘Solacium’ means comfort or solace and, the Greek word ‘Algia’ means pain or suffering was introduced in the year 2003 by the Australian environment philosopher Glenn Albrecht. It collectively describes the emotional suffering or anguish brought on by losing the sense of comfort that comes from one’s home environment, particularly when it experiences major and

unexpected changes. Albrecht especially used the phrase to describe the psychological effects on people and communities of ecological changes like mining, deforestation, and changes brought on by climate change.

The term “Solastalgia” refers to the existential or emotional anguish that arises when one’s home environment significantly changes or deteriorates, frequently as a result of urbanization, pollution, deforestation, or climate change. Solastalgia exhibits a sensation of loss and displacement while remaining physically present in a changing environment, in contrast to nostalgia, which is a yearning for a past time or location. It encapsulates the sorrow and fear experienced when the natural environment, which is closely linked to one’s identity and feeling of place, is harmed or vanishes. By highlighting the inextricable link between people and their ecosystems, this idea draws attention to the psychological effects of environmental change and provides an angle through which to examine how ecological damage influences cultural identity, mental health, and general well-being.

Albrecht (2006) refers “Solastalgia is the lived experience of the loss of value of the present and is manifest in a feeling of dislocation, of being undermined by forces that destroy the potential for solace to be derived from the immediate and given. In brief, he states solastalgia is a form of homesickness one experiences when one is still at home.”

Richard Power’s *The Overstory* is a (2018) novel by Richard Powers that explores humanity’s relationship with trees and the natural world. It follows nine characters influenced by trees, highlighting environmental destruction, activism, and interdependence. The novel blends science, philosophy, and emotion, calling for action and meditation on life’s interconnectedness. *Gold Fame Citrus* (2015) by Claire Vaye Watkins is a dystopian novel set in a future American West, focusing on the struggles of Luz and Ray, a young people in a barren, water-scarce world dominated by the Amargosa Dune Sea. The novel explores themes

of environmental collapse, human resilience, and the longing for belonging in a world ravaged by climate change.

Maja Lunde's novel, *The End of the Ocean* (2019), explores the human relationship with water and its impact on climate change. The story follows Signe, an environmental activist in Norway, who fights against glacier exploitation and personal losses. The novel highlights the emotional impact of water scarcity and serves as a cautionary tale and a deeply human story of resilience. The objective of this proposed research paper critically overviews and analyse the trace of eco-degradation through the perspective of Solastalgia in select novels.

LITERATURE REVIEW

David Glassberg (2014) in his journal article titled *Place, Memory, and Climate Change* condemns the effects of climate change. In fact, he interprets, that many facets of life are changing due to climate change, which is causing historical viewpoints to change as well. By questioning conventional beliefs about naturalness, equality, and inevitableness, historians might help the public comprehend climate change better. With its roots in geography and memory, public history can aid communities in comprehending their environment.

Linda M. Hess (2019) in the article titled '*The Aesthetics of Wonder: Networks of the Grievable in Richard Powers's The Overstory*' expands grievability as 'apprehension of the precariousness of life' beyond the human realm. Powers accomplishes this, in particular, by highlighting the numerous connections between people and trees and by evoking awe at these animals for how they surpass humanity's finite existence and mimic human behaviour. At the same time, it traces the novel's plot that is focused on examining grievability mechanisms.

Crownshaw and Richard (2022) in a book chapter titled '*Meta-Critical Climate Change Fiction: Claire Vaye Watkin's Gold Fame Citrus*' explores the relationship between ecocriticism and speculative climate change fiction. Themes like desertification, harsh weather,

poisonous environments, and ecological collapse are all explored in Watkin's story. According to the chapter, Watkin's story both foreshadows and challenges paradigmatic theorization, exposing her writing as a type of meta-critical fiction. It draws attention to the history of environmental injustice and brutality as well as eco-critical complications in the representations of the Anthropocene.

METHODOLOGY

This research article follows qualitative research analysis and intertextual analysis as a base structure, while three different works acknowledge the prominent ecological degradation and its impacts due to climate change.

DISCUSSION

The Overstory by Richard Powers explores the theme of eco-degradation through the lives of its characters and the narrative of deforestation and environmental collapse. The novel depicts the devastation of ancient forests, industrial logging, and urban expansion, disrupting the interconnectedness of life and causing loss and imbalance. Powers uses trees as a metaphor for the interdependence of all living things, emphasizing the urgent need to recognize the consequences of eco-degradation and reconsider humanity's relationship with the natural world. "Deforestation: a bigger changer of climate than all of the transportation put together." (Powers 261)

The protagonists in Richard Power's *The Overstory* experience severe solastalgia as they witness the forests they depend on and cherish being destroyed. It's the silent pain of witnessing something essential gradually vanishing before your very eyes and feeling powerless to stop it. The realisation that the trees Patricia Westerford has studied those old creatures with which she has a strong bond, are being destroyed for financial gain is the source

of her suffering. She sees the world going on despite the quiet collapse of nature, even though she is aware of how much we are losing on scientific grounds. Her sorrow is not limited to trees; it also stems from the loss of something holy, something that she feels all people ought to value.

Olivia Vandergriff's solastalgia experience is distinct yet equally impactful. She experiences the frailty of existence after surviving a near-death encounter, and this weakness permeates her surroundings. For her, the destruction of trees is a deeply emotional matter rather than merely an ecological one. As the trees are being cut down, she feels as though she is witnessing fragments of her soul disappear. Her anguish motivates her to take action and find purpose in the struggle to protect what remains. She is driven by this anguish to pursue something greater than herself, even if it means fighting a powerful wave of devastation.

The grief gets deeply ingrained in Adam Appich. He feels disengaged, torn between his technical knowledge and the emotional burden of it all, even though he is aware of what is occurring in the world. Even amid a throng, his solastalgia makes him feel alone, as though the world is going on without him, and he is left to bear this burdensome realisation. He is affected by a quiet, hidden type of grief, but it also motivates him to accomplish more, even if he is unsure of what that is.

“Humans carry around legacy behaviours and biases, jerry-rigged holdovers from earlier stages of evolution that follow their own obsolete rules. What seems like erratic, irrational choices are, in fact, strategies created long ago for solving other kinds of problems. We're all trapped in the bodies of sly, social-climbing opportunities shaped to survive the savanna by policing each other.” (Powers 63-64)

Essentially, *The Overstory* employs the concept of solastalgia to examine how closely we are tied to nature. And how as it begins to disappear, more than simply landscapes we lose pieces of who we are. It's an account of the agony we experience when the things we treasure

most, the ones that make us feel at home, are taken away. It's the melancholy realisation that the world we once knew might never be the same.

The post-apocalyptic setting of Claire Vaye Watkin's novel *Gold Fame Citrus*, in which the ecosystem has been ravaged by human resource extraction and climate change, allows the story to examine ecological deterioration. The story takes place in a near-future California that has been reduced to dry empty land by resource depletion and severe droughts. The creation of the enormous, altering Amargosa Dune Sea represents how carelessly humans have treated the planet, accelerating ecological collapse and desertification.

Claire Vaye Watkins evidently captures the severe psychological effects of living in a world altered by climate change in *Gold Fame Citrus* by carefully integrating the concept of solastalgia the emotional misery brought on by environmental degradation into the context of the narrative. Ecological collapse is starkly depicted in the novel's setting, a near-future California engulfed by drought and encircled by the huge and shifting Amargosa Dune Sea. For those who had lived there, this changed environment is unrecognisable, causing a deep sense of displacement and loss.

"I don't know, maybe it's easier to be lost than found. At least there's energy in lostness. Something to be done. I know we're supposed to trust the place, to embrace its mystery, to keep our eyes open..." (Watkins 147)

The terrain itself takes on a personality of its own, representing the irreparable harm caused by human activity. In addition to representing physical devastation, the spreading sandstorms, deserted cities, and drought-stricken ground also represent the emotional break between people and their surroundings. The protagonists are forced to face a world that no longer supports or reflects their recollections of a rich and bountiful past as a result of these

changes. This sensation of loss is especially felt by the main character, Luz. Her disjointed memories of a friendlier, greener California collide with the brutal reality of her current situation, making her feel even more alone and hopeless. The fundamental feature of solastalgia, the inability to reconcile the past with a deteriorated and unrecognisable present is highlighted by this conflict between memory and reality.

Solastalgia's psychological effects go beyond personal feelings to include sadness in society. Desiccated orchards, parched reservoirs, and deserted swimming pools are among the ruins of civilisation that haunt the novel's shattered world, a thriving human existence that has been wiped out by environmental catastrophe. These relics heighten the general sensation of lamenting a world gone, and the government's poor handling of the situation makes people feel even more abandoned and despondent. As they realise the absurdity of such promises in the face of irreparable ruin, the protagonist's desperation gets worse by media advocating an unreal 'Better Place'.

A major issue in Maja Lunde's *The End of the Ocean* is ecological destruction, which is shown through two intertwined timelines. Signe, a Norwegian environmental campaigner, observes in 2017 how industrial exploitation is destroying glaciers, signifying the contempt for nature on the part of humanity. In 2041, David and his daughter Lou travel through Europe devastated by water scarcity and drought, where social disintegration and mass relocation have resulted from desertification. Lunde eloquently illustrates the psychological and physical costs of environmental collapse, demonstrating how severe harm results from human exploitation of natural resources. The novel's warning story highlights just how urgently environmental negligence must be addressed in order to avert the disastrous future it predicts.

Solastalgia, or the grief and emotional pain brought on by the deterioration of one's home environment, is weaved throughout Maja Lunde's *The End of the Ocean*, influencing the character's experiences and mental states. The novel's two time frames, which cover 2017 and

2041 underline the psychological toll of ecological deterioration and provide a detailed investigation of how destruction of the environment affects people and communities.

In the 2017 plot, an elderly environmental activist named Signe suffers from solastalgia as a result of the rapid changes brought about by human activity in her native Norway. Glacier destruction is a metaphor for the exploitation of natural resources for financial gain without considering the long-term effects. As she observes these magnificent ice creations being destroyed, Signe's sorrow is evident since she knows that the scenery she cherished will be permanently changed once they are gone. Her life is dislocated as a result of this loss because the place seems alien and unfriendly.

“It is strange – no, surreal is the word – that I’m one of them, the old people, when I am still so completely myself through and through, the same person I have always been; whether I am fifteen, thirty-five or fifty, I am a constant, unchanged mass, like the person I am in a dream, like a stone, like one-thousand year old ice. My age is disconnected from me, only when I move does its presence become perceptible- then it makes itself known through all its pains...” (Lunde 9)

The 2041 timeline, in which David and his daughter Lou fight to survive in a Europe ravaged by climate change, reflects the solastalgia elements in Signe's novel. Once-fertile areas have become desolate wastelands due to drought, desertification, and water constraints. As he attempts to shield his daughter in a world that no longer provides the resources and security they once took for granted, David suffers from severe solastalgia. A major aspect of David's experience is the emotional strain of attempting to maintain some sort of normalcy for Lou while the natural environment around them collapses. His yearning for an unachievable past highlights the psychological toll that solastalgia takes.

Lou has a unique perspective on solastalgia because she was born into a changed society. She feels emotionally cut off from nature after inheriting a degraded and sparse landscape. The land is a reminder of the life, vegetation, and water that are lost. The character's emotional suffering is connected to the places they used to know and love, demonstrating how the environmental changes are not just physical but also profoundly psychological. Signe's anguish stems from the loss of a world she still remembers, whereas David's sorrow is more about his incapacity to shield his daughter from a dismal future. This underscores the generational nature of solastalgia. Being born into a world that is beyond repair causes Lou to experience solastalgia as a sensation of dislocation.

The way that Lunde depicts solastalgia emphasizes how closely humans and their surroundings are interwoven. In addition to providing a setting for human existence, the natural world also serves as a source of cultural, emotional, and individual identity. People's nostalgic past, feelings of purpose, and sense of belonging diminish along with the environment. Since society as a whole must face the terrible effects of ecological neglect, the pain and loss that define solastalgia are experienced collectively as well as individually. *The End of the Ocean* is a compelling examination of exactly how environmental deterioration alters not just the physical environment but also the mental and emotional landscapes of its inhabitants.

CONCLUSION

The End of the Ocean, *Gold Fame Citrus*, and *The Overstory* are three pieces that examine the emotional and ecological connections between people and the environment. The desolation of a drought-stricken California is portrayed in *Gold Fame Citrus*, while *The Overstory* highlights the close connections between people and woods. In *The End of the Ocean*, the significant societal and emotional effects of humanity's need for water and fertile lands are emphasized, as is the significance of their extinction. In a world where the ecosystem

is collapsing, these pieces illustrate the widespread and long-lasting effects of solastalgia and the immediate need to restore and protect our planet. Because of the deterioration of the natural environment, solastalgia and climate change are related, resulting in emotional and psychological suffering. Droughts, deforestation, and rising temperatures all result in significant loss and disruption, underscoring the interdependence of people and their surroundings. To create a society where solastalgia is not a chronic ailment, addressing environmental issues is not only ecologically vital but also a way to protect the mental and social wellness of present and future generations.

FURTHER SCOPE

- 1) Impacts of climate change on psychological well-being or mental health.
- 2) Eco psychological distress due to unprecedented catastrophes.
- 3) Climate mitigation as an urgent advocacy under SDG.

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